

RESEARCH ON CUTTING FORCE AND DELAMINATION DURING MILLING CFRP WITH VARIOUS WORKPIECE INCLINATION ANGLES

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ABSTRACT

CFRP laminates with varied top/bottom fiber direction angle were trimmed at various workpiece inclination angles. The cutting forces were measured and delaminations were observed while model for type I and type I / II delamination were established and verified. The results indicate that top/bottom fiber direction angles determine the numbers of damaged plies and the 0° fiber direction ply on the top/bottom is able to prevent the development of damaged ply. Force perpendicular to the laminate plane (F_z) increase and force along the path of the advancing tool (F_y) decrease with the increase of workpiece inclination angle. The uncut chip becomes longer and thinner while its volume always keeps constant with the increase of workpiece inclination angle. Model for type I delamination is effective when the depth of damaged bottom laminate layer is large. Moldings for type I / II delamination can predict the actual curvature radius of the fiber bundles.

1 INTRODUCTION

The popularity of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) in the aerospace industry has been increasing thanks to their desirable mechanical and physical properties [1]. Despite the fact that CFRP are mostly produced near net shape, machining is often required in order to bring the component into dimensional requirements and prepare it for assembly. Conventional machining processes such as milling, turning and drilling are most used for this purpose [1-2].

Research on machining CFRP has been on-going for over 20 years, a great deal of contributions have been done by many researchers. Due to the anisotropic and inhomogeneous material properties of CFRP laminates, fiber directions are usually the first thought during machining CFRP. Hintze et al. [3] investigated the delamination during slotting of CFRP and found that top layer fiber (cutting) angle had great influence on the occurrence and propagation of delamination. Work by El-Hofy et al. [4] showed that finished surface with different fiber directions had different surface morphology and the best surface was found on plies where the fibers were parallel to the tool feed/cutting direction. Modeling of mechanistic force by Kalla D [5] and Karpal Y [6] showed that cutting forces were closely related to fiber angles. Gururaja S et al [7-8] studied the stress distribution due to inclined line loads in CFRP and found that the fiber stress and failure form transformed with the combinations of different fiber and line loads orientations. However, many machining defects such as fiber pull-out, matrix smearing, cracking even delamination may occur due to the overlarge machining force or the resultant force with improper direction, peculiarly the thrust force during drilling of CFRP. Heisel U et al [9] observed that increasing point angles resulted in poorer drill hole qualities at the exit (mainly delamination). Work by Faraz A et al [10] showed that the cutting edge rounding correlations with quantitative delamination results were noticed quite comparable to those of the conventional flank wear via statistical linear regression analyses. Publications of delamination during the drilling of CFRP are numerous [11-15], while little attention has been put on milling processes comparatively. Colligan K and Ramulu M [16-17] characterized typical forms of delamination during contour milling

of CFRP and came to the conclusion that delamination during machining mainly resulted from poor support of the top laminate layers.

However, almost all CFRP laminates were clamped horizontally on the workbench and cutting tool axis was definitely perpendicular to the laminate plane in available publishing researches. It's impossible to keep cutting tool axis perpendicular to CFRP laminates all the time because of complicated structure of CFRP workpiece. Solution to trimming such structure is to keep feed along the tangential direction especially when the machining operation is conducted on a 3-axis CNC machining center. In this paper, trimming experiments of CFRP were carried out by using a diamond coated cemented carbide tool with the combination of different workpiece inclination angles and fiber directions. The relationship between cutting force and force bearing status of workpiece were studied. Delamination forms of laminate layer were observed. At the same time, the formation mechanism of different delamination forms was discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS AND PROCEDURES

The CFRP laminates are fabricated from IMS/X850 prepreps with T800 carbon fibers. The lay-up of the multidirectional CFRP composites laminates is $[(45^\circ/0^\circ/135^\circ/90^\circ)_6]_s$ and the fiber volume fraction is 65%. Each laminate has 48 plies, so CFRP laminates have a thickness of 9mm. The laminates are cut into 200mm \times 150mm using diamond-edged saw to fit the clamp. The mechanical properties are listed in Table 1. All milling experiments have been carried out on a DMG Ultrasonic 20 Linear as shown in Fig. 1(a). The DMG Ultrasonic 20 Linear has maximum spindle speed of 42 000rpm and maximum feed speed of 5 m/min. The experimental data are collected with a data acquisition system composed of a 9272 Kistler dynamometer and a 5070A Kistler amplifier. The fixation of the composite material laminate is made as shown in Fig. 1(b), to make sure that vibrations and displacement are eliminated. The CVD diamond coated end-mill has been employed to avoid the effect of tool wear on the cutting force. The end-mill as shown in Fig.1(c) is 10mm in diameter with 12 flutes and helical angle of 13.6° .

Engineering constant		Identification
E_{11}	[GPa]	168
E_{12}	[GPa]	9.25
ν_{12}	-	0.35
G_{12}	[GPa]	6.0
V_f	[%]	65

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of CFRP laminates.

Figure 1: (a) The experimental equipments, (b) Fixation of the composite material, (c) End-mill.

Fiber direction angle φ was defined clockwise from carbon fiber axis to feed direction (Fig. 2(a)). Four fiber direction angles (0° , 45° , 90° , 135°) were studied. As shown in Fig. 2(b), the tool feed direction always kept constant along the length direction of workpiece. Equivalent axis depth of cut a_p can be represented with equation (1) by considering workpiece inclination angle θ and laminate thickness L . Workpiece inclination angle θ was determined by considering the helical angle of milling

cutter by rotating the A-axis of the machine tool. Details for machining process were available in Table 2.

Figure 2: (a) Definition of fiber angle (b) Diagram of machining process

Types	Contents
Machine tool	DMG Ultrasonic 20 Linear
Milling mode	Down-milling
Spindle speed	10000 r/min
Cutting speed v	324 m/min
Feed speed v_f	4000 mm/min
Radial depth of cut a_e	1 mm
Workpiece inclination angle θ	13.6° , 28.6° , 43.6° , 58.6°
Cooling fluid	Emulsified liquid; 5 % dilution;

Table 2 Details for trimming of CFRP laminates

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Cutting force and measured force bearing status of workpiece

Fig. 3 displays the measured cutting forces (F_x , F_y , F_z) as a function of workpiece inclination angle θ and fiber direction angle ϕ . It's obvious that the cutting forces (F_x , F_y , F_z) always keep the same only if the numbers of each ply with different fiber direction angles and the whole laminate plate keep constant thickness.

Figure 3: Variation trend of cutting forces (F_x , F_y , F_z)

It's interesting to found that cutting forces (F_y, F_z) have obvious variation trend with the increase of workpiece inclination angle θ . In fact, the effect of workpiece inclination angle θ is to determine the forces bearing status of workpiece (F_y, F_z), while overlarge value of F_z may results in delamination because of the poor support of the top laminate layers [16-17].

It's well known that radial depth of cut a_e , axis depth of cut a_p , feed per tooth f_{z-h} , etc have different influences on cutting forces. According to work by Chen [18] and Shaw [19], the instantaneous uncut chip thickness h varies continuous with engagement angle ψ , and is maximum at the exit angle ψ_Σ . Hence, the average uncut chip thickness h_m was adopted during this experiment as shown in Fig. 4 and Eq. 2.

Figure 4: Diagram of uncut chip thickness and sectional area

$$f_{z-h} = \frac{v_{f-h}}{N \cdot Z} \quad (2)$$

$$h_m = \frac{1}{\psi_\Sigma} \int_0^{\psi_\Sigma} f_{z-h} \sin \psi d\psi = \frac{f_{z-h} a_e}{5 \arccos(1 - a_e/5)}$$

Where f_{z-h} is feed per tooth along the horizontal direction; N is the tool spindle speed; Z is the number of cutter flutes; h_m is the average uncut chip thickness; ψ is instantaneous engagement angle; ψ_Σ is the exit angle; a_e is the radial depth of cut; R is the tool radius.

Sectional area of uncut chip S was obtained according to the geometrical relationship between the tool and workpiece (Eq. 3). Length of uncut chip (axis depth of cut a_p) and volume of uncut chip V were available in Eq. 1 and Eq. 4.

$$S = \int_{-\sqrt{2a_e R - a_e^2}}^{\frac{1}{2}f_{z-h}} (a_e - R + \sqrt{R^2 - x^2}) dx - \int_{\frac{1}{2}f_{z-h} - \sqrt{2a_e R - a_e^2}}^{\frac{1}{2}f_{z-h}} (a_e - R + \sqrt{R^2 - (x - f_{z-h})^2}) dx$$

$$= 25 \cdot \arcsin \frac{f_{z-h}}{10} - 5f_{z-h} + a_e \cdot f_{z-h} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot f_{z-h} \cdot \sqrt{25 - \frac{f_{z-h}^2}{4}} \quad (3)$$

$$\approx 25 \cdot \frac{f_{z-h}}{10} - 5f_{z-h} + a_e \cdot f_{z-h} + \frac{5}{2} \cdot f_{z-h}$$

$$= a_e \cdot f_{z-h}$$

$$V = S \times a_p = \frac{a_e \cdot v_f \cdot L}{N \cdot Z} \quad (4)$$

As shown in Fig. 5, the average uncut chip thickness h_m and sectional area of uncut chip S decrease, and the axis depth of cut a_p increases with the increase of workpiece inclination angle θ . While the volume of uncut chip V always keeps the same no matter how workpiece inclination angle θ . changes which is verified by Eq. 4. In other words, with the increase of workpiece inclination angle θ , the uncut chip becomes thinner and longer while its volume keeps constant at the same time.

3.2 Influences of workpiece inclination angle and fiber direction angles on delamination

According work by Sheikh-Ahmad et al [20], delamination of top/bottom laminate layer can be classified into four types (Fig. 6). Surface topographies of bottom layer and finished surface with various workpiece inclination angles and fiber direction angles are as shown in Fig. 7-Fig. 10. It can be found that the delamination forms are significant different at various combinations of workpiece

inclination angles and fiber direction angles.

Figure 5: Influences of workpiece inclination angle on (a) average uncut chip thickness; (b) sectional area of uncut chip; (c) equivalent axis depth of cut; (d) volume of uncut chip

Figure 6: Classification of delamination at different forms [20]

Type III delamination has the smallest damage among four types of delamination, and can only be found on laminate with 0° fiber direction angle when the workpiece inclination angle is 58.6° (Fig. 7 (d)). Type I delamination can be found on laminate with 45° and 90° fiber direction angle when the workpiece inclination angle is less than 58.6° (Fig. 8 (a, b, c), Fig. 9 (a, b, c)). Type II delamination can be found on laminate with 135° fiber direction angle when the workpiece inclination angle is less than 58.6° (Fig. 10 (a, b, c)). However, when the workpiece inclination angle reaches its maximum value ($\theta=58.6^\circ$), abrupt change to type I / II delamination can be observed on Fig. 8 (d), Fig. 9 (d) and Fig. 10 (d). And the length of fiber protrusions on bottom layer is about 1mm which is equivalent to the radial depth of cut. According to the analysis of measured forces bearing status of workpiece (F_x , F_y , F_z) in section 3.1, force F_z reaches its maximum value when the workpiece inclination angle is 58.6° which can result in bend of fiber bundles.

Figure 7: Surface topographies of bottom layer and finished surface with various workpiece inclination angles (fiber direction angle $\varphi=0^\circ$)

Figure 8: Surface topographies of bottom layer and finished surface with various workpiece inclined angles (fiber direction angle $\varphi=45^\circ$)

Figure 9: Surface topographies of bottom layer and finished surface with various workpiece inclined angles (fiber direction angle $\varphi=90^\circ$)

Figure 10: Surface topographies of bottom layer and finished surface with various workpiece inclined angles (fiber direction angle $\varphi=135^\circ$)

In order to quantify the proportion of each type of delamination in a given sample length ($L=10\text{cm}$), length of each type of delamination was measured along machined edge direction (Fig. 11). Type III delamination occurs only on the laminates with 0° fiber direction angle and is hard to measure, so the type III delamination was not taken into consideration. As shown in Fig. 11 (a) and (b), the proportion of each type of delamination has the same variation trend that the type I and type I / II delamination are the main parts while type II delamination is negligible. While the domain type of delamination is type II and type I / II on top/bottom laminate layer with 135° fiber direction angle. It's observed that the fiber direction has great influence on the type of delamination and the workpiece inclination angle determines the proportion of each type of delamination expect a special cast that the delamination form turns into type I / II when the workpiece inclination angle is 58.6° . However, analysis of bottom laminate ply is not enough to assess the level of damaged laminates. Numbers of

damaged laminate plies were available in Fig. 12 as a function of workpiece inclination angles and fiber direction angles. Influence of workpiece inclined angle on forces bearing status of workpiece F_z and numbers of damaged plies share the same trend. However, with the increase of fiber direction angle, numbers of damaged plies increase gradually which don't correspond to the variation trend of force F_z . The greatest numbers of damaged plies ($\theta=58.6^\circ$) are 1, 2, 3 and 4 layers at a given fiber direction angle of 0° , 45° , 90° and 135° respectively which is just the 0° fiber direction ply of each stacking sequences. The results indicate that the 0° fiber direction ply has the ability to prevent the development of damaged ply and the tool feed direction should keep along the fiber axis direction to avoid severe delamination.

Figure 11: Proportion of each type of delamination (a) $\varphi=45^\circ$, (b) $\varphi=90^\circ$, (c) $\varphi=135^\circ$

Figure 12: Numbers of damaged plies

3.3 Molding and analysis of different types of delamination

According to molding of delamination by Hintze [21], there are two deflection mechanisms of fiber bundles, i.e. bending of fiber bundle in and perpendicular to the laminate plane. For $0^\circ < \varphi < 90^\circ$, bending of fiber bundle will occur perpendicular to the laminate plane (Fig. 7(a) - (d)).

For $90^\circ < \text{fiber direction angle } \varphi < 180^\circ$, bending of fiber bundle will occur in the laminate plane (Fig. 9(a) - (d)). As for $\varphi=90^\circ$, the probability of both deflection mechanisms are equal, while only bending of fiber bundle perpendicular is observed in Fig. 8(a) - (d). On the basis of classification of each type of delamination in section 3.2, type I and I/II delamination are caused by the bending of fiber bundle perpendicular to the laminate plane and type II delamination is caused by the bending or twisting of fiber bundle in the laminate plane. Fiber bundles in type I delamination are broken and cut by the tool, which just bend or move away from the path of the advancing tool and then spring back to its original orientation during type I/II and II delamination [20].

The reason why the fibers deflect without being broken is that their transverse rupture strain is not attained [21]. A minimal fiber curvature radius r_{\min} was introduced in Eq. 5 [21].

$$r_{\min} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon_B} - 1 \right) \cdot d \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta = r_{\min} \cdot \sin \varphi + d \quad (6)$$

Where the ultimate tensile strain ε_B is 1.8% for T800 carbon fiber; d is the thickness of fiber bundle; Δ is the depth of damaged bottom laminate layer as shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14.

Figure 13: Profile of type I delamination on bottom layer with 45° fiber direction angle

Figure 14: Profile of type I delamination on bottom layer with 90° fiber direction angle

The sectional profile of type I delamination is symmetrical and similar to a quadratic curve. Because the thickness of fiber bundle d varies continuously, an equivalent thickness of fiber bundle d_{eq} is adopted in Fig. 15. The area s and width w are kept unchanged, so the equivalent thickness of fiber bundle d_{eq} is only the function of maximum thickness of fiber bundle d_{max} as shown in Eq. 7.

The theoretical thickness of fiber bundle is obtained from Eq. 5 and Eq. 6. The measured equivalent thicknesses of fiber bundle are available in Table 3 which quite agrees with the theoretical value. The results show that the bending molding is a good predictor for the thickness of fiber bundle.

Figure 15: Determination of equivalent thickness of fiber bundle $/d_{eq}$

$$y = \frac{4 \cdot d_{max}}{w^2} \cdot x^2 - d_{max}$$

$$s = \int_{\frac{w}{2}}^{\frac{w}{2}} (d_{max} - \frac{4 \cdot d_{max}}{w^2} \cdot x^2) dx = \frac{2}{3} d_{max} \cdot w \quad (7)$$

$$d_{eq} = \frac{s}{w} = \frac{2}{3} d_{max}$$

Fiber direction angle $\varphi/^\circ$	45			90		
Depth of delamination $\Delta/\mu\text{m}$	1692.24			1690.46		
Region	a	b	c	a	b	c
Maximum thickness of fiber bundle $d_{max}/\mu\text{m}$	118.15	124.04	127.52	89.14	90.27	92.64
Equivalent thickness of fiber bundle $d_{eq}/\mu\text{m}$	78.77	82.69	85.01	59.43	60.18	61.76
Theoretical thickness of fiber bundle $d/\mu\text{m}$	83.40			59.78		

Table 4 Thickness of fiber bundle for Fig. 13 and Fig. 14

Figure 16: Morphology of type I delamination (a) $\varphi=45^\circ$, (b) $\varphi=90^\circ$

However, the profile of delamination becomes difficult to measure when depth of damaged bottom laminate layer Δ is quite small. The grooved morphologies in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 turn into serrate boundary in Fig. 16. As shown in Table 4, the theoretical thickness of fiber bundle d is much smaller than the equivalent thickness of fiber bundle d_{eq} . In fact, the serrate boundary is caused by the break of fiber bundles which occur very close and frequent. Adjacent fractures caused by delamination are overlapping which can make the actual measured thickness is much larger than the theoretical thickness of fiber bundle.

Fiber direction angle $\varphi/^\circ$	45	90
Depth of delamination $\Delta/\mu\text{m}$	297.769	683.471
Maximum thickness of fiber bundle $d_{max}/\mu\text{m}$	158.170	167.602
Equivalent thickness of fiber bundle $d_{eq}/\mu\text{m}$	105.45	111.73
Theoretical thickness of fiber bundle $d/\mu\text{m}$	14.68	24.17

Table 5 Thickness of fiber bundle for Fig. 16

As for type II delamination, the depth of damaged bottom laminate layer Δ is very small, and the fiber bundle is more narrow and thinner which can twist more easily under the combined actions of measured force bearing status of workpiece F_y and F_z . So the curvature radius for fiber bundle is hard to decide. However, fiber bundle caused by type I / II delamination is much wider and thicker (Fig. 8(d), 9(d) and 10(d)), which is easy to bend perpendicular to the laminate plane instead of twisting in the laminate plane.

As shown in Fig. 17, the depth of delamination on bottom layer $L_{I/II}$ is 6.65mm, and the thickness of fiber bundle d is 200.11 μm . According to the analysis above, instead of broken or fracture, the fiber bundles just bend or move away from the path of the advancing tool and then spring back to its original orientation [20]. The actual curvature radius r should be larger than the minimal fiber curvature radius r_{min} .

Figure 17: (a) Depth of delamination; (b) Thickness of fiber bundles with 90° fiber direction angle

The fiber bundles bending molding of type I / II delamination with 90° fiber direction layer is available in Fig. 18. The length of fiber protrusions on bottom layer is about 1mm which is equivalent to the radial depth of cut. The actual curvature radius r can be obtained in Eq. 8 according to the geometrical relationship in Fig. 18. Modified equation can be found in Eq. 9 by considering the influence of fiber direction angle. Since the depth of delamination on bottom layer $L_{I/II}$ is 6.649mm, the actual curvature radius r is 6.679mm. According to Eq. 5, the minimal fiber curvature radius r_{min} is 5.660mm when the thickness of fiber bundle d is 200.113 μm as shown in Fig. 17 (b). It's obvious that the actual curvature radius r is larger than the minimal fiber curvature radius r_{min} , so the fiber bundles are just bending instead of broken or fracture. The result shows that the molding for type I / II delamination can predict the actual curvature radius r of the fiber bundles.

Figure 18: Bending of fiber bundles on bottom layer with 90° fiber direction angle

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{L_{VII}}{r} \\ r \cdot \sin \alpha + a_e = L_{VII} \end{cases} \Rightarrow r \cdot \sin \frac{L_{VII}}{r} + a_e = L_{VII} \quad (8)$$

$$r \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot \sin \frac{L_{VII}}{r \sin \varphi} + a_e = L_{VII} \quad (9)$$

4 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results obtained from the experiments, the following conclusions could be extracted.

(1) Force perpendicular to the laminate plane (F_z) increase and force along the path of the advancing tool (F_y) decrease with the increase of workpiece inclination angle, while the cutting forces always keep constant at the same time.

(2) The fiber direction has great influence on the type of delamination and the workpiece inclination angle determines the proportion of each type of delamination expect a special cast that the delamination form turns into type I / II when the workpiece inclination angle is 58.6°. The uncut chip becomes longer and thinner while its volume always keeps constant with the increase of workpiece inclination angle. Stacking sequences of each ply have great influence on the numbers of damaged plies and the 0° fiber direction ply has the ability to prevent the development of damaged ply.

(3) Model for type I delamination is effective when the depth of damaged bottom laminate layer is large. However, it doesn't work well when the depth of damaged bottom laminate layer is small. Models for type I / II delamination can predict the actual curvature radius r of the fiber bundles.

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